

COMPARISON OF CEREBROPLACENTAL RATIO WITH UMBILICAL ARTERY WAVEFORM IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RESTRICTION ASSOCIATED WITH HYPERTENSIVE PREGNANCIES

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Abstract

Objective: To determine the diagnostic accuracy of cerebroplacental ratio and umbilical artery waveform in the diagnosis of intrauterine growth restriction in hypertensive pregnancies taking birth weight as gold standard.

Study Design: Cross-sectional, validation study

Study place and period: Gynecology Department, Punjab Rangers Teaching Hospital, Lahore from 16 March 2025 till 16 June 2025

Methodology: One hundred and sixty one women were enrolled from OPD and underwent Doppler ultrasonography. On Doppler, CPR and UA waveform were recorded. Women were labeled as positive or negative for IUGR. Then women were followed-up until delivery and at time of delivery, birth weight of baby was noted. If fetal weight <10th percentile on birth for particular gestational age, then IUGR was labeled. All the data will be recorded in proforma.

Results: The median age of pregnant women was 31.00 (IQR: 15.50) years. The mean duration of diagnosis of gestational hypertension was 4.00 (IQR: 3.00) weeks. In this study, CPR showed Sensitivity of 83.7%, Specificity of 86.7%, PPV of 87.8%, NPV of 82.3% and Diagnostic accuracy of 87.0%. The UA showed Sensitivity of 74.4%, Specificity of 89.3%, PPV of 88.9%, NPV of 75.3% and Diagnostic accuracy of 81.4%.

Conclusion: The accuracy of CPR is better and more reliable than UA in diagnosing IUGR.

INTRODUCTION:

After 20 weeks of gestation, maternal hypertension is defined as a systolic blood pressure of at least 140 mmHg and a diastolic blood pressure of at least 90 mmHg on at least two occasions, separated by at least six hours.^{1,2} The primary cause of maternal and fetal morbidity and mortality, notwithstanding recent advancements in prenatal care, is hypertension diseases. The failure of the fetus to reach its innate growth potential is known as intrauterine

growth restriction.^{3,4} The reported prevalence of IUGR is about 65% in pregnancies associated with hypertension.⁵ One of the primary objectives of obstetrical practice in the third trimester is the prediction of perinatal problems in pregnancies close or at term.⁶ In this case, managing pregnancies impacted by fetal growth restriction was much enhanced by the use of Doppler ultrasound for fetal surveillance to assess fetal hemodynamics. This resulted in lower rates of perinatal morbidity

and mortality.^{7,8} A higher risk of perinatal death, morbidity, and poor neurodevelopment is linked to intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR). Fetuses with IUGR, those with small constitutions, and those with acceptable growth (misdiagnosed as small) are among the diverse group of small-for-gestational-age fetuses that can be identified by ultrasound biometry. The most comprehensive noninvasive diagnostic for fetal health is umbilical arterial (UA) Doppler velocimetry.^{9,10} Fetal hypoxemia can be detected by the cerebroplacental ratio (CPR), which is the ratio of the S/D of MCA to that of UA. This can happen through two separate mechanisms: decreased MCA resistance and increased placental resistance, which is indicated by a drop in UA S/D.^{11,12}

Rationale of this study is to assess the diagnostic accuracy of CPR and UA waveform in the diagnosis of IUGR in hypertensive pregnancies. Literature showed that Doppler is a good modality to diagnose IUGR in hypertensive pregnancies. But CPR and UA waveform showed ambiguity in accuracy for prediction of IUGR. Moreover, no local evidence exist in literature that can help us to determine whether which waveform is more reliable. Therefore we want to conduct this study to get evidence in favor of clinical diagnosis of IUGR, so that in future instead of going for less accurate method, we can replace better diagnostic option with diagnosis and management of IUGR in hypertensive pregnancies.

METHODOLOGY:

After taking approval from ethical review committee, this cross-sectional, validation study was conducted at Gynecology Department, Punjab Rangers Teaching Hospital, Lahore from 16 March 2025 till 16 June 2025. By using sensitivity and specificity calculator, sample size of 161 cases is calculated with confidence interval 95%, percentage of IUGR i.e. 65%⁵ and sensitivity of UA waveform i.e. 75.8% and specificity of CPR i.e. 41.2% with 13% margin of error.¹³ All the pregnant women who fulfilled following selection criteria were enrolled only by using Non-probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Inclusion: Pregnant women of age 18-45 years, parity <5, gestational age >20 weeks, diagnosed

with pregnancy induced hypertension. Hypertensive pregnancy was defined as presence of BP \geq 140/90 mmHg on two occasions 4 hours apart after 20 weeks of pregnancy.

Exclusion criteria: Any pathology like multiple pregnancies, anomalous fetuses, intrauterine abnormal placenta (like accreta, previa, abruptio) fetal demise, AFI <5 or >21 cm (on ultrasound), with antepartum hemorrhage, diabetes (BSR>186 mg/dl), severe anemia (hb<9 g/dl), chronic hypertension (BP \geq 140/90 mmHg before pregnancy or in first trimester or on anti-hypertensive medication), proteinuria (>+1 on dipstick method) were not included.

The informed consent was taken from women. Demographic details like age, BMI, gestational age, parity, residence, occupation, duration of gestational hypertension, were noted. Then women underwent Doppler ultrasonography by an experienced sonologist with assistance of researcher. All evaluations were conducted using a Siemens Acuson Antares Premier Edition ultrasound machine (Siemens AG, Munich, Germany) and a 2-5 MHz probe with a high pass filter. On Doppler, CPR and UA waveform were recorded. Reports were assessed and findings were recorded. Women were labeled as positive or negative for IUGR. On CPR, it was labeled as positive if MCA/UA ratio <1.08 on Doppler. On UA waveform, it was labeled as positive if UA>3 on Doppler. Then women were followed-up until delivery and at time of delivery, birth weight of baby was noted. If fetal weight <10th percentile on birth for particular gestational age, then IUGR was labeled (gold standard). All the data will be recorded in proforma. All the women with hypertension and IUGR were managed efficiently as per standard protocol.

Data was analyzed using SPSS version 24.0. Normality was checked by Shapiro-Wilk test. Quantitative data like age, BMI, gestational age, duration of gestational hypertension, fetal weight, were presented as mean and standard deviation. Qualitative data like residence, occupation, IUGR on CPR, UA and on birth were presented as frequency and percentage. 2x2 tables were generated to calculate sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV and diagnostic accuracy of CPR versus UA waveform taking actual fetal weight as gold standard.

RESULTS

In this study, we applied test Shapiro-Wilk test as test of normality and found most of the variables were not following normal distribution. Thus the findings were presented as median with interquartile range. The median age of pregnant women was 31.00 (IQR: 15.50) years. The median BMI at presentation was 26.00 (IQR: 7.00) kg/m². The median gestational age at presentation was 28.00 (IQR: 6.00) weeks. Out of 161 pregnant women, 37 (23%) were primigravida, 52 (32.3%) were

primiparous while 72 (44.7%) were multiparous. There were also 37 (23%) working women in total study sample. The mean duration of diagnosis of gestational hypertension was 4.00 (IQR: 3.00) weeks. At the time of presentation, the median CPR on ultrasound was detected as 1.06 (IQR: 0.31) while median UA on ultrasound was 2.70 (IQR: 2.45). On birth, the median fetal weight was observed as 1875.00 (IQR: 684.50) grams at median gestational age 38.00 (IQR: 2.00) weeks. Table-I

Figure-1: IUGR detected on ultrasound by using CPR and UA with birth weight on birth

Table-I: Demography and clinical examination of enrolled women (n = 161)

	Statistic
Age of women, years	31.00 (IQR: 15.50)
BMI, kg/m ²	26.00 (IQR: 7.00)
Gestational age at presentation, weeks	28.00 (IQR: 6.00)
Parity	
Primigravida	37 (23%)
Primiparous	52 (32.3%)
Parity 2	46 (28.6%)
Parity 3	26 (16.1%)
Occupation	
Housewife	124 (77%)
Working lady	37 (23%)
Residence	
Rural	30 (18.6%)
Urban	131 (81.4%)
Duration of gestational hypertension, weeks	4.00 (IQR: 3.00)
CPR	1.06 (IQR: 0.31)
UA	2.70 (IQR: 2.45)
Actual Fetal weight, grams	1875.00 (IQR: 684.50)

Gestational age at delivery, weeks	38.00 (IQR: 2.00)
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On CPR, there were 82 (50.9%) neonates with IUGR. On UA, 72 (44.7%) fetuses were positive for IUGR. While on birth, IUGR was positive in 86 (53.4%) cases. Figure-1

In this study, CPR showed Sensitivity of 83.7%, Specificity of 86.7%, PPV of 87.8%, NPV of 82.3% and Diagnostic accuracy of 87.0%. Table-II

Table-II: Accuracy of CPR in detection IUGR with birth weight as gold standard criteria to detect IUGR

		IUGR on birth		Total
		Positive	Negative	
IUGR on CPR	Positive	72	10	82
	Negative	14	65	79
Total		86	75	161

Sensitivity: 83.7%, Specificity: 86.7%, PPV: 87.8%, NPV: 82.3% and Diagnostic accuracy: 87.0%

In this study, UA showed Sensitivity of 74.4%, Specificity of 89.3%, PPV of 88.9%, NPV of

75.3% and Diagnostic accuracy of 81.4%. Table-III

Table-III: Accuracy of UA in detection IUGR with birth weight as gold standard criteria to detect IUGR

		IUGR on birth		Total
		Positive	Negative	
IUGR on UA	Positive	64	8	72
	Negative	22	67	89
Total		86	75	161

Sensitivity: 74.4%, Specificity: 89.3%, PPV: 88.9%, NPV: 75.3% and Diagnostic accuracy: 81.4%

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DISCUSSION

In this study, CPR showed Sensitivity of 83.7%, Specificity of 86.7%, PPV of 87.8%, NPV of 82.3% and Diagnostic accuracy of 87.0%. The UA showed Sensitivity of 74.4%, Specificity of 89.3%, PPV of 88.9%, NPV of 75.3% and Diagnostic accuracy of 81.4%. One of the main causes of neonatal morbidity is IUGR, which is frequently connected to placental insufficiency. Fetal growth restriction sometimes coexists with hypertensive diseases, which can change the course of the condition.¹⁴

In a related study, Konwar et al. found that the UA waveform had a sensitivity of 75.8% and a specificity of 41.2% for the diagnosis of IUGR in 50 pregnant women with pregnancy-induced hypertension, whereas the CPR had a sensitivity of 66.7% and a specificity of 76.5%. According to their findings, CPR is a useful predictor of poor perinatal outcomes in cases of pregnancy-induced hypertension. Doppler investigations of several vessels may be useful in managing high-risk pregnancies because they may reveal

information about the fetus that is susceptible to placental insufficiency and hypoxia.¹³ In another study, Malik et al. examined 100 pregnant women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and found that CPR had a sensitivity of 55.17% and a specificity of 100% for IUGR diagnosis. According to their findings, the CPR should be regularly computed during obstetrical Doppler for antepartum fetal surveillance in cases of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy since it is a more accurate indicator of unfavorable perinatal outcomes. It proposed that the Doppler ultrasonography machine's software may be calibrated to provide CPR on a regular basis in high-risk pregnancies.¹¹

According to a different study by Mahajan et al. on 138 pregnant women, the UA waveform demonstrated sensitivity and specificity for the diagnosis of IUGR of 58.13% and 91.58%, respectively. They came to the conclusion that in women with pregnancy-induced hypertension, aberrant Doppler indices in the UA, such as an elevated S/D ratio, RI, and PI, seem to be useful

indicators of poor fetal outcomes. In addition to improving the management of pregnancies complicated by hypertensive pregnancies, monitoring these indicators can help with risk classification.¹⁵ In a comparative cross-sectional investigation, Oyekale et al. performed Doppler ultrasounds on 75 pregnant women with pregnancy-induced hypertension and 75 healthy pregnant women. They found that while the mean CPR was significantly lower for those with pregnancy-induced hypertension than for those without (1.178 ± 0.207 vs. 1.288 ± 0.156 ; $p = 0.001$), the mean UA-RI was significantly higher in the cases group compared to the control group (0.67 ± 0.14 vs. 0.61 ± 0.08 ; $p = 0.012$).¹⁶ The predictive value of CPR for composite unfavorable perinatal outcomes showed high specificity and PPV of 100% each, with a diagnostic accuracy of 74% and a sensitivity of 55.17%, according to a study by Malik et al. This indicates that there is a strong link between the CPR and unfavorable perinatal outcomes. When compared to other Doppler indices, CPR demonstrated superior sensitivity (55.17%), specificity (100%), PPV (100%), and NPV (61.76%) for forecasting worse perinatal outcomes (S/D ratio of UA with $p < 0.001$). According to a comparative analysis of diagnostic accuracy, the CPR was more accurate than the UA at 74% in predicting unfavorable perinatal outcomes in cases of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.¹¹ Women with pregnancy-induced hypertension between 28 and 40 weeks of gestation were examined for umbilical artery and middle cerebral artery Doppler waveforms in the Smitha et al. research. They found that when it came to predicting unfavorable perinatal outcomes, CPR outperformed UA-PI in terms of sensitivity (94.42%), PPV (86.42%), and accuracy (90%).¹⁷ According to a number of recent studies, CPR may be helpful in identifying elevated placental vascular resistance in fetuses that are not affected by IUGR. This suggests that CPR may be useful in predicting perinatal outcomes in this small subset of placental insufficiency without IUGR, and as a result, it may be used as a screening test for perinatal impairment in the general population.¹⁸ Even though a low CPR is linked to a poor perinatal outcome at term, the lack of diagnostic precision makes it difficult to use

CPR as a screening method.^{19, 20}

CONCLUSION

The accuracy of CPR is better and more reliable than UA in diagnosing IUGR. Now the ambiguity has been resolved and CPR is found to be more reliable. So in future, we will use CPR for diagnosis of IUGR and estimation of fetal weight, instead of using less accurate methods and can replace better diagnostic option with diagnosis and management of IUGR in hypertensive pregnancies.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None.

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